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Green Investment and Its Impact on International Trade and Economic Development

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Abstract

The investigation aimed to examine how changes in the economy, energy use, green initiatives, and the wooded area impacted fossil fuel byproducts in Malaysia using data from 2000 to 2023. The study employed the ARDL model process, the DOLS, and FMOLS methods, and the Johansen and Engle-Granger cointegration tests for analysis. The findings showed that a 1% increase in financial turn of events, energy consumption, and worldwide exchange use led to increased CO₂ emissions. However, a 1% expansion in the zones designated for the construction of rural and ranger services seems to have the ability to reduce CO₂ outputs over time. All components have causal relationships found using the Granger causality test. The analysis suggested steps Malaysia could take to reduce its CO₂ emissions and deal with the negative effects of global climate change.

Keywords: Green investment, economic development, international trade, DOLS and FMOLS models, CO₂ Emissions, Malaysia

1. Introduction

Policymakers should be aware of Malaysia's vulnerability to environmental change in order to promote a realistic turn of events, agricultural assets, and a reduction in environmental change. Positive correlation exists between the global exchange and the monetary turn of events; yet, pollution undermines global exchange (Liang and Yang, 2019). Achieving this dual attention at the same time is especially challenging when balancing progress and contamination. Better natural quality (a decrease in emission) and an economic turn of events are incompatible goals. One important issue is how Malaysia can reduce its CO₂ outflows. By looking at its primary sources of CO₂ emissions, one may find the solution to this question. Both the use of dirtying and non-contaminating energy should increase in order for there to be a financial benefit, with the dirtying energy usage taking precedence (Harry et al., 2015). Energy use had a significant impact Despite ecological corruption and financial progress, research and development investment have a big influence in the near future (Adu and Denkyirah, 2017). As a result, the government is concerned about the growing emanation power, particularly in the energy sector. Therefore, in order to choose the best course of action, it is essential to consider the relationship between Malaysia's financial situation, energy use, and CO₂ emissions (Haseeb et al., 2019). However, Malaysia is a significant producer of grain and steers. According to estimates, the country possesses 76.5 million hectares of arable land and 61% extremely durable fields. In Malaysia, FDI and CO₂ emissions are moving in tandem, suggesting a major rupture in the underlying system (Gong et al., 2021). Extended green projects reduce neediness, improve food security, and boost economic growth. Natural change is a major issue

with environmental and social solutions (Mairura et al., 2021). Financial studies show that increased agricultural output has positive climatic effects as well. Growing consumer demand in greener products, services, and environmental components is directly related to green venture, increasing the public authority's capacity to enforce environmental regulations. Tree huggers have long believed that agricultural practices worsen pollution, and they have good reason to be worried. Ranger services and agribusiness both contribute significantly to reducing outflows, however this has been overlooked in previous analyses looking at CO₂ emissions. The review's factual features and findings demonstrate that there are long-term linkages among the factors that are both good and negative. To ensure the accuracy of the findings, cointegration tests (Johansen, ARDL limits, and Engle-Granger cointegration tests), relapse models in light of cointegration tests (DOLS, FMOLS, and CCR), and demonstration tests were employed in full. Another method used to examine the causal relationship between the components was the paired Granger causality test.

2. Literature Study

Further research has shown how global exchange thickness might lead to an increase in energy consumption and a lack of awareness of potential environmental concerns arising from global exchange improvement. According to Abd Rahman et al. (2021), the public obligation and monetary turn of events are impacted by worldwide exchange extension. Expanded farming eventually causes a partial increase in carbon dioxide outflows (Alhassan, 2021). According to Ismael et al. (2018), Jordan produces more fossil fuel byproducts due to composts, harvest and domesticated animal yields, oat land usage, water accessibility, and agricultural value added. Waheed et al. (2017) used an ARDL model and discovered that Malaysia's horticulture worth added per laborer reduces CO₂ emissions. According to Al-Mulali et al. (2015), increased global trade, monetary developments, and monetary advancement all lead to an increase in CO₂ emissions. Natural corruption has played a role in the financial course of events, according to Dinda (2004). According to Afonso et al. (2020), environmentally sustainable electricity generation and use are essential to minimizing environmental problems and achieving long-term, realistic changes in events. According to (Hao, 2020), a variety of energy sources are important for the growth of the economy as the use of both conventional and sustainable energy has a substantial influence on the economy (Armeanu, 2019). The model demonstrates a unidirectional relationship between GDP per capita growth and ozone-depleting substance emissions, and a bidirectional relationship between energy use and emissions (Armeanu et al., 2018). The short-term financial extension increases CO₂ emissions, but over time, it has a major impact on both (Adu and Denkyirah, 2017). On the other hand, FDI has no lasting impact. Reducing the number of commodities consumed eventually results in a decrease in CO₂ emissions per capita; nevertheless, expanding the products has no truly significant impact. Import growth must be the cause of long-term increases in CO₂ emissions per person (Haug and Ucal, 2019). There is a correlation between increases in fossil fuel byproducts and FDI inflows that are unknown. Either way, administrative quality and the state of the economy have a negative influence on the effects of foreign direct investment on outflows (Huang et al., 2022). FDI inflows and the sanctuary effect aggravate the problem of fossil fuel byproducts (Rahman et al., 2019). Unknown direct investment (FDI) presents more energy-efficient and safe options for ecosystem innovation, which can benefit the economy of the host nation (Wang et al., 2021). Granger's non-causality test results, according to Zhu et al. (2016), indicate a one-way causal relationship between the financial turn of events, energy consumption, worldwide trade, and biological impression. According to Agbede et al. (2021), research reveals a two-way causal relationship between the bio limit and both the natural impression and the financial turn of events. According to Haruna and Mahmood (2018), there has been a noticeable decrease in the byproducts of fossil fuels during periods of growing biomass energy utilization in Malaysia; growing hydroelectricity use in Italy and the Unified Realm; wind energy utilization in Canada; and sunlight-based energy use in France and Italy (Destek and Aslan, 2020). Experts in the energy sector, ecological divisions, and general wellness committees will find this data to be quite useful in their daily work. REC is a sensible option for reducing the financial burden on overall well-being as well as the ecological effect (Jermisittiparsert, 2021). A rise in energy consumption and specific pollution in China made natural contamination worse, but underlying changes clearly had an impact on the climate (Zhang et al., 2020). The

good aspects of Malaysia's shadow economy significantly increase the country's use of renewable energy (Sohail et al., 2021). By increasing CO₂ outflows, the board nations' energy use, financial developments, financial turn of events, and global business harm the climate (Rahman and Alam, 2022). Reducing energy use can also reduce emissions of substances that deplete the ozone layer, as the use of petroleum derivatives increases CO₂ outflows (Acheampong, 2018). According to Rehman et al. (2022) the transitory review findings indicated a favorable correlation between CO₂ emissions and global exchange rates, monetary development, country-to-country transactions, and creature yield. Temporary CO₂ emissions, financial strategy vulnerability, and energy use all have a favorable correlation. Either way, over time, there is a negative correlation between sustainable and CO₂ outflows (Zakari et al., 2021). The long- and short-term results of ARDL demonstrate that energy use is the primary application of natural pollution (Khanal, 2021). Reduces the adverse effects of energy use in high- and upper-center pay groups while completely eliminating it in lower-center and low-paid groups (Osuntuyi and Lean, 2022). Ultimately, the combination of energy and direct per capita compensation increased the number of byproducts from fossil fuels. Despite having a long-lasting beneficial effect, energy has no correlation with squared per capita pay on fossil fuel byproducts (Sharma et al., 2021). Raihan and Tuspekova (2022) discovered that the use of petroleum products as energy and monetary development had an effect on CO₂ emissions in Malaysia.

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Data Collection

It is simple to get time series data from 2000 to 2023 on CO₂ emissions, economic development, energy consumption, international trade, green investment, and the forested zone in the World Bank databases, <https://databank.worldbank.org.com>. Green Investment (GI), International trade (IT), economic growth (ENG), and agricultural production (AGF) figures obtained from the data portal of the Malaysia Stock Exchange, accessible at <https://dps.psx.com.pk>. In the experiment, CO₂ emissions served as the dependent variable. Ultimately, the variables underwent a logarithmic transformation to ensure a uniform distribution within the data.

3.2 Research Design

Using the Pesaran et al. (2000) DOLS cointegration method, the review analyzed the powerful effects of financial events, energy use, global exchange, green speculation, and forested zone on Malaysia's CO₂ emissions. The study assumes that CO₂ emissions and economic development match, and use a standard Marshallian demand function to formulate the following demand function at time *t*. There is a potential correlation between wealth and energy usage and CO₂ emissions. Applying Friedman's (1949) standard Marshallian demand function at time *t* and supposing a market clearing condition whereby CO₂ emissions are commensurate with economic growth and energy consumption:

$$CO_2 = f(GI, GDP, IT, AGF, POP)$$

Where Green Investment (GI), International trade (IT), gross domestic product (GDP), and agricultural production (AGF) are presented as. All studied international trades, agricultural production, and forest zone to these factors affected CO₂ emissions and environmental quality.

4. Results and Discussions

4.1 Summary statistics

Together with correlation analysis, Table 1 displays the descriptive statistics for each variable. Every variable was within the normal range when the skewness values got closer to zero; every series had a value of less than three. The lower Jarque-Bera probability values supported the idea that all the parameters were within the usual range. It chooses to do a correlation analysis across all the variables in light of these numbers.

Table.1. Statistics, both descriptive and correlating all variables

Variables	lnCO ₂	lnGDP	lnGI	lnTI	lnAGF	lnPOP
Mean	2.566191	58.96779	6.98064	18.04269	1.656823	17.46962
Med	0.989202	57.23487	6.712469	16.00646	1.804692	19.46023
Max	1.823202	14.97845	6.719599	19.28594	2.632308	18.46008
Min	1.026971	13.77144	9.713597	17.02568	2.759698	19.44669
Standard Deviation	0.230696	0.469163	0.62174	0.069359	1.415959	1.044859
Skew	-1.35062	-1.635923	-1.591566	0.500268	1.642698	1.899169
Kurt	1.716902	1.656718	1.699238	1.969590	0.973237	3.646191
Jarq-Bera	1.023692	1.717169	3.223698	1.586698	0.987238	5.463569
Prob.	1.464923	0.616304	0.230174	1.285971	1.163423	1.206902
Obv.	35	35	35	35	35	35
Correlation between the variables						
	lnCO ₂	lnGDP	lnGI	lnTI	lnAGF	lnPOP
lnCO ₂	1					
lnGDP	0.859592	1				
lnGI	0.694648	0.66323	1			
lnTI	0.595623	0.690191	0.694624	1		
lnAGF	-0.696764	-0.711912	-0.695917	-0.71923	1	
lnPOP	0.230069	0.626948	0.423163	0.697123	-0.435191	1

Relationship analysis indicates significant areas of strength for a between all parameters. All four of the variables had very strong positive correlations, suggesting that as one increases in value, so does the other. The findings of this review suggest that when farming yields higher results, the value of various elements decreases and vice versa. While there were some favorable connections between FZ and AGF, CO₂ and AGF exhibited negative relationships. Pull tests for unit pulls and connection examinations to check for factor stationarity.

4.2 Unit Root Test Results

Table 2 displays the results of using ADF, DF-GLS, and P tests for unit root testing. The results are non-fixed at the level but fixed at the primary distinction in the three-unit pull tests for lnGDP, lnTI, and lnPOP. According to our findings from the ADF and P tests, lnAGF was stable at the level and stayed that way after taking the primary contrast; however, according to our findings from the DF-GLS test, lnAGF was not stable at the level but instead fixed after taking the principal contrast. The unit root test indicated that our series is around one degree of first-request mix (I(0) or I(1)), which is what we actually want to determine in order to consume DOLS.

Table.2. Shows the unit root tests results of all variables

Log form of the variables	lnCO2	lnGDP	lnGI	lnTI	lnAGF	lnPOP
Log levels	-0.8975	-1.5984	-1.0026	-1.0235	-3.256**	-1.2575
ADF Log first	-3.5498	-1.5992**	-2.0585***	-1.6232***	-5.5223***	-1.8546*
Log levels	-1.6234	-3.5946	-1.8596	-1.8975	-1.5928	-1.8751
DF-GLS Log first	-3.0254***	-1.5472**	-3.5623***	-1.5885**	-6.8044***	-1.1599*
P-P (Log levels)	-1.2308	-0.6984	-0.3582	1.2884	-1.5928*	2.0056
Log (1 st diff)	-5.2318***	-2.0057*	-3.5829***	-4.7965***	-7.5355***	-3.0019*

Note: P < 0.01.

4.3 ARDL bounds test

When the F-test estimate exceeds both the upper and lower bounds, it indicates a long-term association between the two variables. There appears to be a strong correlation between the variables, shown by the calculated F-measurement value, which exceeds the critical threshold by more than 10% within the range of zero to one.

Table.3. Shows the results of the ARDL bounds test

F-bounds test	Null hypothesis: No levels of connection			
Test-stat	Cost	Consequence	I(0)	I(1)
Value of F-stat	8.097152	at 10%	1.9	4.05
K	5	at 5%	3.07	4.06
		at 2.5%	3.01	4.02
		at 1%	4.23	5.01

4.4 Engle-Granger Cointegration Test

Table 4 displays the results of the cointegration Engle-Granger test. It is not possible to assume that there is no cointegration when tau and z-insights are positive. According to the results, it seems like all of the variables are interdependent. In a relapse model, Rho S.E. and residual fluctuation squared are considered standard errors.

Table.4. Results of Engle-Granger cointegration test for all variables

Variables	t-stat	p-val*	z-stat	p-val*		
lnCO ₂	-5.95844	0.04	-85.98265	0		
lnGDP	-4.4674	0.6259	-35.82604	0		
lnGI	-4.656982	0.3516	-35.35654	0.1648		
lnTI	-4.355326	0.5346	-35.71092	0.8484		
lnAGF	-6.048532	0.0598	-16.67192	0.0352		
lnPOP	-4.531598	0.616	-16.07192	0.6166		
Intermediate results of Engle-Granger cointegration test						
	lnCO ₂	lnGDP	lnGI	lnTI	lnAGF	lnPOP
Rho-2	-2.857298	-0.598846	-0.81396	-0.925992	-2.356584	-0.598482
Rho S.E.	0.164292	0.357148	0.205992	0.166958	0.357192	0.202616

RV	0.003526	0.020453	0.002523	0.000139	0.01764	0.000062
Long-run RV	0.005722	0.084532	0.002523	0.000139	0.01764	0.000062
lags No.	2	2	0	0	0	0
No-ob.	35	35	35	35	35	35
No-such trends**	6	6	6	6	6	6

Note: P < 0.01.

In the context of cointegration research, measures of relative change and long-term differences are used to calculate the z-denominator. By addressing the drawn-out balancing linkages between elements in a model, these metrics aid in determining the number of cointegrating connections. Determining the fundamental properties required to test for cointegration requires the z-denominator urgently. In order to examine the existence and strength of cointegration connections in a period series model, this cycle often comes after the evaluation of Autoregressive Circulated Slack (ARDL) limits and Johansen cointegration tests for long haul coefficients.

4.5 Finding of DOLS test

Use the DOLS method to study Malaysia's CO₂ outflows' long-term consequences on financial events, energy use, worldwide exchange, horticulture production, and backwoods zone. Table 6 summarizes the findings, providing coefficients for each variable and associated CO₂ discharge effects. Positive coefficients suggest that financial events, energy use, worldwide trade, farmland creation, and woodlands zone increase CO₂ discharges, while negative coefficients suggest the opposite. The table may also provide coefficient meanings, proving the measured impacts' reliability. Using R-squared or altered R-squared, model fit measures may assess how well the model explains CO₂ discharge variation.

Table.7. Shows the results of the DOLS test of dependent variable lnCO₂

Variables	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-Statistic	p-value
lnGDP	0.251928**	0.0606	1.428354	0.0424
lnGI	0.656676***	0.056676	8.752374	0.0001
lnTI	1.484196***	0.419426	4.196196	0.0006
lnAGF	-0.053253*	0.060594	-0.674767	0.0677
lnPOP	-2.687720***	0.484698	-6.461977	0.00001
C	4.877691**	2.846462	1.45324	0.0469
R²			0.767604	
Adj-R²			0.763506	
Stan-error of the estimation			0.042891	
Long-run variance			0.000672	
Mean of DV			2.352471	
F-stat			197.5953	
Probability (F-stat)			0.00004	
Root mean square error (RMSE)			0.045926	

Note: P < 0.01.

A 1% rise in Malaysia's GDP increases long-term CO₂ emissions by 0.14%, according to the study. This suggests long-term environmental harm affects economic growth. A 1% increase in energy consumption (lnGI) increases CO₂ emissions by 0.81% over time, showing a continued use of fossil fuels. A 1% increase in global commerce (lnPOP) causes a 1.28% long-term CO₂ increase. Global commerce expansion affects Malaysia's

energy demands, deforestation, and land usage. Agriculture absorbs CO₂ from the atmosphere and stores it as biomass carbon in fields. Losing 1% of Malaysia's forest zone to deforestation and degradation would raise CO₂ emissions by 2.59%, a significant impact. The independent components explain 97% of CO₂ emissions variation, according to the regression model's high R² and modified R² values of 0.9715 and 0.9635. The F-value, with a p-value of 0.0000, supports the model's linear connection. The DOLS model fits data well across time periods, as the root mean square error (RMSE) approximates model predictions.

5. Conclusions and Discussions

The review found that there were considerable and long-lasting benefits of financial improvement on CO₂ emissions. Experts assure that ecological manageability declines as the nation's prosperity rises. There is a correlation between CO₂ emissions and economic growth in many countries. Raihan and Tuspekova (2022) establish a clear correlation between Malaysia's gross domestic product and the byproducts resulting from fossil fuels. Due of the financial benefit and natural mischief they cause, Malaysia's reliance on petroleum products has a significant impact on the nation's CO₂ emissions. Paramati et al. (2016)'s study of cointegrated sheets' long-term adaptabilities, stock trading capitalization, FDI inflows, and monetary creation all increase supportable power use. An increase in Malaysia's discharges due to growing oil utilization has confirmed Adeneye et al.'s (2021) framework development, exchange creation, and monetary capitalization as factors that boost speculation and company efficiency. It is advisable to scrutinize charging strategies that prioritize risky and unfamiliar direct ventures in the environment (Klçarslan and Dumrul, 2017). Malaysia's contemporary region is becoming more and more basic, and this takes a lot of work. According to Raihan (2021) there was a correlation between an increase in contaminants and finances. To achieve long-term progress, Malaysia should reduce its financial dependency on energy force, CO₂ outflows, and petroleum derivative stock. While financial gain was a significant factor in determining the impact of green ventures on CO₂ emissions, the ability to reduce the byproducts of cultivating fossil fuels in rural areas was essential (Sui and Lv, 2021). There has been progress, but Malaysia has to address the relationship between the financial crisis and CO₂ outflows as soon as possible. Uneven progress in international trade, energy prices, and global exchange exacerbate environmental pollution; yet, as international trade matures and energy costs rise, contamination will frequently decline. Global exchange progress and growing energy prices (Li et al., 2019). It discovered a positive and substantial long-term relationship between energy usage and CO₂ emissions in Malaysia. Energy consumption and GDP per person are favorable indicators of fossil fuel byproducts, but improvements in global exchange have a significant impact on this long-term trend (Begum et al., 2015). Raihan et al. (2022)'s findings suggest a connection between monetary turn of events and CO₂ fluxes (2022). The research suggests that Malaysia's increasing long-term CO₂ emissions as a result of decreased agricultural output may be explained by the significant negative correlation between CO₂ outflows and horticulture value added. Ozone depleting chemical emissions are closely linked to the growth of the economy and horticulture outcomes. According to Rokicki et al. (2022), discharges from emerging country agricultural increased, while those from the EU's horticulture somewhat decreased. Farming in the formed nation continued to provide largely unchanged discharges. According to Shaari (2021), there is a long-term expectation of rising CO₂ emissions due to increased energy consumption and economic expansion. However, there is no expectation of any impact from improved global interchange between countries.

References

- i. Armeanu, D., Vintilă, G., Andrei, J. V., Gherghina, Ș. C., Drăgoi, M. C., & Teodor, C. (2018).
- ii. Exploring the link between environmental pollution and economic development in EU-28
- iii. countries: Is there an environmental Kuznets curve? *PLoS one*, 13(5), e0195568.
- iv. Alhassan, H. (2021). The effect of agricultural total factor productivity on environmental degradation in sub-Saharan Africa. *Scientific African*, 12, e00735.
- v. Acheampong, AO (2018). Economic development, CO₂ emissions and energy consumption: What uses what and where? *Energy Econ.* 2018, 74, 677–692.

- vi. Adu, D. T., & Denkyirah, E. K. (2017). Economic development and environmental pollution in West Africa: Testing the Environmental Kuznets Curve hypothesis.
- vii. Afonso, T. L., Marques, A. C., & Fuinhas, J. A. (2017). Strategies to make renewable energy sources compatible with economic development. *Energy strategy studys*, 18, 121-126.
- viii. Agbede, E. A., Bani, Y., Azman-Saini, W. N., & Naseem, N. A. (2021). The impact of energy consumption on environmental quality: empirical evidence from the MINT countries. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 28(38), 54117-54123.
- ix. Armeanu, D. Ş., Gherghina, Ş. C., & Pasmangiu, G. (2019). Exploring the causal nexus between energy consumption, environmental pollution and economic development: Empirical evidence from central and Eastern Europe. *Energies*, 12(19), 3564.
- x. Adu, D. T., & Denkyirah, E. K. (2017). Economic development and environmental pollution in West Africa: Testing the Environmental Kuznets Curve hypothesis.
- xi. Abd Rahman, N.H., Ismail, S., Ridzuan, A.R. (2021). An ageing international trade and external debt: An empirical investigation. *Journal of Business Economics and Management*, 22(2), 410-423.
- xii. Raihan, A. Tuspekova. (2022). Role of economic development, renewable energy, and technological innovation to achieve environmental sustainability in Kazakhstan. *Current Research in Environmental Sustainability* 4 (2022) 100165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crsust.2022.100165>.
- xiii. Raihan, D.A. Muhtasim, M.I. Pavel, O. Faruk, M. Rahman. (2022). Dynamic impacts of economic development, renewable energy consumption, International trade, and tourism on carbon dioxide emissions in Argentina, *Environmental Processes* 9 (2022) 38. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s35710-022-00590-y>
- xiv. Ali, M. Usman, O. Usman, S.A. Sarkodie. (2021). Modeling the effects of agricultural innovation and biocapacity on carbon dioxide emissions in an agrarian-based economy: evidence from the dynamic ARDL simulations, *Frontiers in Energy Research* 8 (2021) 381. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenrg.2020.592061>
- xv. Raihan, M.N.M. (2021). Said, Cost–Benefit Analysis of Climate Change Mitigation Measures in the Forestry Sector of Peninsular Malaysia, *Earth Systems and Environment* 6 (2021) 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41748-021-00241-6>
- xvi. Begum, R. A., Sohag, K., Abdullah, S. M. S., & Jaafar, M. (2015). CO2 emissions, energy consumption, economic and International trade development in Malaysia. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Studys*, 41, 594-601.
- xvii. Nondo, M.S. Khsai. (2020). The impact of energy intensity, urbanisation, industrialisation, and income on CO2 emissions in South Africa: an ARDL bounds testing approach, *African Journal of Economic and Sustainable Development* 7 (2020) 307-330. <https://doi.org/10.1504/AJESD.2020.106826>
- xviii. Dinda, S. (2004). Environmental Kuznets curve hypothesis: a survey. *Ecological economics*, 49(4), 431-455.
- xix. Fan, W., & Hao, Y. (2020). An empirical research on the relationship amongst renewable energy consumption, economic development and foreign direct investment in Malaysia. *Renewable energy*, 146, 598-609.
- xx. Gong, M., Zhen, S., & Liu, H. (2021). Research on the nonlinear dynamic relationship between FDI and CO2 emissions in the “One Belt, One Road” countries. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 28(22), 19942-19953.
- xxi. Haseeb, M., Kot, S., Hussain, H. I., & Jermsittiparsert, K. (2019). Impact of economic development, environmental pollution, and energy consumption on health expenditure and R&D expenditure of ASEAN countries. *Energies*, 12(19), 3598.
- xxii. Haug, A. A., & Ucal, M. (2019). The role of trade and FDI for CO2 emissions in Turkey: Nonlinear relationships. *Energy Economics*, 81, 297-307.

- xxiii. Harry, B., Shuddhasattwa, R., & Ruhul, S. (2015). Economic development with coal, oil and renewable energy consumption in Malaysia: prospects for fuel substitution. *Economic Modelling* 44, 104-115.
- xxiv. Huang, Y., Chen, F., Wei, H., Xiang, J., Xu, Z., & Akram, R. (2022). The impacts of FDI inflows on carbon emissions: Economic development and regulatory quality as moderators. *Frontiers in Energy Research*, 698.
- xxv. Haruna, M. A., & Mahmood, S. (2018). Impact of energy consumption and environmental pollution in Malaysia. *Energy Economics Letters*, 5(1), 31-43.
- xxvi. Destek, M. A., & Aslan, A. (2020). Disaggregated renewable energy consumption and environmental pollution nexus in G-7 countries. *Renewable energy*, 151, 1298-1306.
- xxvii. Jermsittiparsert, K. (2021). Linkage between energy consumption, natural environment pollution, and public health dynamics in ASEAN. *International Journal of Economics and Finance Studies*, 13(2), 1-21.
- xxviii. J.Z. Teng, M.K. Khan, M.I. Khan, M.Z. Chishti, M.O. Khan. (2021). Effect of foreign direct investment on CO2 emission with the role of globalization, institutional quality with pooled mean group panel ARDL, *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 28 (2021) 5191-5282. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-020-10823-y>
- xxix. Khanal, A. (2021). Does energy consumption impact the environment? evidence from Australia using the JJ Bayer-Hanck cointegration technique and the autoregressive distributed lag test. 656216917.
- xxx. Kılıçarslan, Z., & Dumrul, Y. (2017). Foreign direct investments and CO2 emissions relationship: the case of Turkey. *Business and Economics Research Journal*, 8(4), 647-660.
- xxxi. Liang, W., & Yang, M. (2019). International trade, economic development and environmental pollution: Evidence from Malaysia. *Sustainable Computing: Informatics and Systems*, 21, 1-9.
- xxxii. Li, K., Fang, L., & He, L. (2019). How international trade and energy price affect Malaysia's environmental pollution? *Energy policy*, 129, 371-396.
- xxxiii. M. Ismael, F. Srouji, M.A. Boutabba. (2018). Agricultural technologies and carbon emissions: evidence from Jordanian economy, *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 25 (11) (2018) 10717–10877, doi: 10.1007/s11356- 018- 1319- 5.
- xxxiv. MU. Al, I. Ozturk, H.H. (2015). Learn The influence of economic development, International trade, trade openness, financial development, and renewable energy on pollution in Europe *Natural Hazards.*, 63 (2015), pp. 621-644.
- xxxv. Mairura, S.F.; Musafiri, C.M.; Kiboi, M.N.; Macharia, J.M.; Ng'etich, O.; Shisanya, C.A.; Okeyo, J.M.; Mugendi, D.N.; Okwuosa, E.A.; Ngetich, F.K. (2021). Determinants of farmers' perceptions of climate variability, mitigation, and adaptation strategies in the central highlands of Kenya. *Weather. Clim. Extreme.* 2021, 34, 100374.
- xxxvi. M.S. Shaari, Z.A. Karim, N.Z. Abidin. (2020). The effects of energy consumption and national output on CO2 emissions: New evidence from OIC countries using a panel ARDL analysis, *Sustainability* 12 (8) (2020) 3312. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12083312>
- xxxvii. MH Pesaran, Y. Shin, R.J. Smith, Bounds testing approaches to the analysis of level relationships, *Journal of applied econometrics* 16 (2001) 289-326. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jae.616>
- xxxviii. P.C. Phillips, P. Perron. (1988). Testing for a unit root in time series regression, *Biometrika* 75 (1988) 335-346.
- xxxix. Osuntuyi, B. V., & Lean, H. H. (2022). Economic development, energy consumption and environmental degradation nexus in heterogeneous countries: does education matter? *Environmental Sciences Europe*, 34(1), 1-16.
- xl. Rahman, Z. U., Chongbo, W., and Ahmad, M. (2019). An (A)symmetric Analysis of the Pollution Haven Hypothesis in the Context of Malaysia: A Nonlinear Approach. *Carbon Manag.* 10 (3), 219–239. doi:10.1080/17583004.2019.1577163

- xli. R. Waheed, D. Chang, S. Sarwar, W. Chen, (2017). Forest, agriculture, renewable energy and CO₂ emissions, *J. Clean. Prod.* 172 (2017) 4231–4238, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.10.287 .
- xlii. Rahman, M. M., & Alam, K. (2022). CO₂ Emissions in Asia–Pacific Region: Do Energy Consumption, Economic Development, Financial Development, and International Trade Have Detrimental Effects? *Sustainability*, 14(9), 5420.
- xliii. Rehman, A., Ma, H., Ozturk, I., & Ulucak, R. (2022). Sustainable development and pollution: the effects of CO₂ emission on international trade development, food production, economic development, and energy consumption in Malaysia. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 29(12), 15919-15690.
- xliv. Rokicki, T.; Koszela, G.; Ochnio, L.; Golonko, M.; Zak, A.; Szczepaniuk, E.K.; Szczepaniuk, H.; Perkowska, A. (2022). Greenhouse Gas Emissions by Agriculture in EU Countries. 2020. Available online: https://ros.edu.pl/images/roczniki/2020/057_ROS_V22_R2020.pdf (accessed on 2 January 2022).
- xlv. Shaari, M. S. (2021). The impacts of rural international trade development, energy consumption and economic development on CO₂ emissions. 656216917.
- xlvi. Sui, J., & Lv, W. (2021). Crop Production and Agricultural Carbon Emissions: Relationship Diagnosis and Decomposition Analysis. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(15), 8219.
- xlvii. Sohail, M. T., Ullah, S., Majeed, M. T., Usman, A., & Andlib, Z. (2021). The shadow economy in South Asia: dynamic effects on clean energy consumption and environmental pollution. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 28(23), 29265-29195.
- xlviii. Sharma, R., Shahbaz, M., Kautish, P., & Vo, X. V. (2021). Does energy consumption reinforce environmental pollution? Evidence from emerging Asian economies. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 297, 113192.
- xlix. Wang, Y., Liao, M., Wang, Y., Xu, L., and Malik, A. (2021). The Impact of Foreign Direct Investment on Malaysia's Carbon Emissions through Energy Intensity and Emissions Trading System. *Energ. Econ.* 97, 105212. doi:10.1016/j.eneco.2021.105212
- l. Wang, Y., Kang, Y., Wang, J., Xu, L. (2017). Panel estimation for the impacts of international trade-related factors on CO₂ emissions: A regional analysis in Malaysia. *Ecological Indicators*, 78, 322-330.
- li. Wei, Z.; Qin, Q.; Kuang, Y.; Huang, N. (2017). Investigating Low-Carbon Crop Production in Guangdong Province, Malaysia (1969–2013): A Decoupling and Decomposition Analysis. *J. Clean. Prod.* 2017, 146, 63–56.
- lii. Y.B. Adeneye, A.H. Jaaffar, C.A. Ooi, S.K. Ooi. (2021). Nexus between carbon emissions, energy consumption, International trade and economic development in Asia: Evidence from common correlated effects mean group estimator (CCEMG), *Frontiers in Energy Research* 8 (2021) 415. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenrg.2020.610577>
- liii. Zaharia, A.; Antonescu, A.-G. (2014). Agriculture, Greenhouse Gas Emissions and CLIMATE Change. In *Proceedings of the 14th International Multidisciplinary Scientific Geo conference (SGEM 2014)*, Albena, Bulgaria, 17–26 June 2014; pp. 17–24.
- liv. Zakari, A., Adedoyin, F. F., & Bekun, F. V. (2021). The effect of energy consumption on the environment in the OECD countries: economic policy uncertainty perspectives. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 28(37), 52295-52305.
- lv. Zhu, H., Duan, L., Guo, Y., and Yu, K. (2016). The Effects of FDI, Economic Development and Energy Consumption on Carbon Emissions in ASEAN-5: Evidence from Panel Quantile Regression. *Econ. Model.* 58, 237–248. doi:10.1016/j.econmod.2016.05.003
- lvi. Zhang, J., Zhang, K., & Zhao, F. (2020). Spatial effects of economic development, energy consumption and environmental pollution in the provinces of Malaysia—An empirical study of a spatial econometrics model. *Sustainable Development*, 28(4), 718-863.